

**YONG‘IN SHAROITIDA QURILISH MATERIALLARIDA SODIR BO‘LADIGAN
ASOSIY HOSSALAR VA JARAYONLAR**

Siddiqova Madinabonu

SamDAQU magistranti.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12684499>

Mexanik xossalar. Egilishga mustahkamlik chegarasini aniqlash

$$R_{eg} = \frac{3 \cdot P_{buz} \cdot L}{2 \cdot b \cdot h^2}, \text{ MPa}$$

bu yerda; R_{buz} , P_{buz} - namunaga qo‘yilgan yuk, kg

L - tayanchlar orasidagi masofa, sm

b - namuna ko‘ndalang kesimining eni, sm

h^2 - namuna ko‘ndalang kesimining balandligi, sm

Misol: 1200 g gips olinadi suvga solinadi, 60 sekund davomida aralashtirilib moylangan qolipga solinadi. 2 soatdan so‘ng 4x4x16 sm o‘lchamli namuna MII-100 qurilmasiga qo‘yilib egilishga bo‘lgan mustahkamligi topiladi. 2ta pastki tayanch orasidagi masofa 100 mm. Egilishga mustahkamlik chegarasi, kgs/sm MPa

$$R_{eg} = \frac{3 \cdot P_{buz} \cdot L}{2 \cdot b \cdot h^2} = \frac{3 \cdot 180 \cdot 16}{2 \cdot 4 \cdot 4^2} = 67,5 \text{ MPa}$$

Siqilishga bo‘lgan mustahkamlik chegarasini aniqlash.

$$R_{siq} = \frac{R_{buz}}{F}$$

Misol: Siqilishga bo‘lgan mustahkamlik chegarasini aniqlash uchun 6 ta yarimta balkachalardan foydalanamiz. Yarim balkachalarning tepa va pastki qismiga o‘lchamlari 40x62,5 mm keladigan yani yuzasi 25 sm² bo‘lgan po‘lat listlar qo‘yiladi va gidravlik press yordamida siqilishga bo‘lgan mustahkamlik chegarasi aniqlanadi. Siqilishga mustahkamlik chegarasi, kgs/sm MPa

$$R_{siq} = \frac{R_{buz}}{F} = \frac{10000}{25} = 400 \text{ kgs/sm MPa}$$

Cho‘zilishga bo‘lgan mustahkamlik chegarasini aniqlash.

$$R_{cho'z} = \frac{l_k - l_0}{l_0}$$

bu yerda: l_k - cho‘zilgandan keyingi uzunligi; l_0 - cho‘zilishdan oldingi uzunligi

Misol: Po‘lat armaturani cho‘zilishga mustaxkamligini aniqlaymiz. Berilgan: Po‘lat namunasini cho‘zilishdan oldingi uzunligi 25 sm, cho‘zilgandan keyingi uzunligi 27 sm,

Yechish:

$$R_{cho'z} = \frac{l_k - l_0}{l_0} = \frac{27 - 25}{25} = 0.08sm$$

Ayrim materiallarning vaqtinchalik qarshilik ko‘rsatishining sonli qiymati

Material	Vaqtinchalik qarshilik ko‘rsatishi R, MPa		
	R_{siq}	$R_{cho'z}$	R_{eg}
1. Torf plitalar	0,5	-	0,25- 0,2
2. Oddiy betonlar	5-30	0,6- 2,0	-
3. Yuqori sifatli beton	40-80	2,5- 7,0	-
4. Xom g‘isht	7,5-30	-	1,5- 3,5
5. Yog‘och: tolalariga ko‘ndalang, tolalari bo‘ylab	50 6,5	130 6,5	100 75
6. Shishaplastik	420	450- 470	410- 460
7. Granit	100- 250	2-4,4	-
8. Po‘lat	380- 450	380- 450	-

Deformativlik – absolyut, nisbiy deformatsiya hajmi bo‘yicha material namunasining massasini o‘zgartirmagan holda o‘lchamlarini (shaklini) o‘zgartirish xususiyatidir. Namunalar (buyumlar) ning deformatsiyalanishi siqilishda, cho‘zilishda, surilish, egilishda va boshqa hollarda sodir bo‘ladi.

Egiluvchanlik – ta’sir etayotgan kuch natijasida material namunalarining o‘z shaklini o‘zgartirishi va kuch olingandan so‘ng boshlang‘ich shakliga qaytish xususiyatidir.

Oquvchanlik chegarasi (σ_y)- plastik deformatsiyalar o'sishiga olib keluvchi doimiy kuchlanish

Egiluvchanlik darajasi (σ_y) – materialda qoldiq deformatsiya hosil qilmaydigan maksimal kuchlanish. Materialning deformativ mustahkamlik xarakteristikalarini kuchlanish diagrammasi ifodalaydi. Materialning egilishdagi deformatsiyasi *Guk qonuniga* asosan to'g'ri burchakli kuchlanishlar diagrammasidagi maksimal kuchlanish.

$$\sigma = E\varepsilon ,$$

bu yerda; ε - nisbiy deformatsiya bo'lib, cho'zilishda quyidagi formula bilan aniqlanadi.

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\lambda_1 - \lambda_0}{\lambda_0} ,$$

bu yerda; λ_0 - namunaning cho'zilishgacha bo'lgan uzunligi, m; λ_1 - namunaning cho'zilishdan keyingi uzunligi, m; E - elastiklik (egiluvchanlik) moduli, Pa.

Plastiklik- yuk ta'sirida material namunasining buzilmasdan o'z shaklini o'zgartirishi va yuk olingandan so'ng o'zining yangi shaklini saqlab qolish xususiyati. Materiallarning bu xossasi *oquvchanlik* bilan xarakterlanadi.

Qattqlik – materialga nisbatan ancha qattiq materialning qarshilik ko'rsatish xususiyatidir. Metallar uchun qattqlik darajasi Brenell qiymati bo'yicha (HB) aniqlanadi. Tabiiy tosh materiallarining qattqligi qattqlik shkalasi bo'yicha aniqlaniladi.

Moos qattqlik shkalasi

Minerallar	Kimyoviy tarkibi	Qattqlik ko'rsatkichi
Talk	$Mg_3(OH)_2 \cdot Si_2O_5$	1
Gips	$CaSO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$	2
Kalsiy	$CaCO_3$	3
Eruvchan shisha	CaF_2	4
Apatit	$Ca_5(PO_4)_3 \cdot FCl Ca_5$	5
Ortoklaz	$K(Al \cdot SiO_3 \cdot O_8)$	6
Kvars	SiO_2	7
Topaz	$Al(F \cdot OH) \cdot SiO_2$	8
Korund	Al_2O_3	9

Olmos	S	10
-------	---	----

Shkalada maxsus saralab olingan minerallar shunday ketma-ketlikda joylashtiriladiki, bunda tartib bo'yicha navbatdagi material o'zidan oldingi materialda chiziq qoldiradi, o'zi esa yemirilmaydi.

	Tabiiy holatda		Absolyut holatda		G'ovaklik		Gigroskopi k		Egilishga				Siqilishga		Chuzilis hga	
	m	V	m	V	P	P ₀	m ₁	m	p _{bus}	L	b	h	R _{buz}	F	l _k	l _o
1	740	1.1	1500	1.1	2000	3500	333	110	185	11	3	4	1890	15	25	12
2	735	1.2	2600	1.2	2400	3100	444	122	195	13	4	2	1900	19	29	15
3	725	1.3	2200	1.3	2600	3300	555	135	200	15	2	3	2001	18	30	17
4	743	1.4	2300	1.4	2650	3500	666	145	201	19	3	4	2011	17	33	20
5	770	1.5	2220	1.5	2780	3600	777	155	174	18	4	5	1000	11	41	22
6	750	1.6	2650	1.6	2800	3700	888	175	186	17	5	6	1250	13	44	26
7	743	1.7	2700	1.7	2850	4000	999	300	185	11	6	7	1850	19	27	12
8	730	1.8	2750	1.8	2855	2855	540	300	174	13	7	8	1950	20	26	15
9	725	1.9	2800	1.9	1800	2900	545	250	45	19	8	9	1000	21	25	19
10	738	2.1	2900	2.1	1750	3050	450	150	144	20	9	3	1200	23	27	17
11	741	2.2	3000	2.2	1890	3055	444	145	122	21	3	4	1212	25	28	16
12	750	2.3	3500	2.3	1900	2950	750	450	123	23	4	2	1235	29	29	20
13	751	2.4	3100	2.4	2001	3330	486	230	110	25	2	3	1239	30	30	21
14	760	2.5	3300	2.5	2011	3350	444	290	122	29	3	4	1359	33	31	22
15	765	2.6	3500	2.6	1000	3800	564	320	135	30	4	5	1596	15	35	23
16	744	2.7	3600	2.7	1250	3850	412	230	145	33	5	6	1954	19	33	21
17	750	2.8	3700	2.8	1850	2800	423	210	155	35	6	7	1874	18	45	23
18	755	2.9	4000	2.9	1950	2200	485	205	175	39	7	8	1888	17	44	22
19	764	1.0	2000	1.0	1000	2100	431	207	210	41	8	9	1466	11	43	24
20	740	1.1	2400	1.1	1200	2000	456	234	145	44	9	3	1234	13	42	26
21	770	1.2	2600	1.2	1212	2600	423	210	177	43	3	4	1235	19	40	27
22	780	1.3	2650	1.3	1235	2500	321	211	198	12	4	2	1239	20	19	10
23	775	1.4	2780	1.4	1239	2450	212	109	123	17	2	3	1359	21	18	11
24	790	1.5	2800	1.5	1359	2350	455	209	145	16	3	4	1596	23	17	15
25	795	1.6	2850	1.6	1596	2250	333	246	164	15	4	5	1954	25	16	10

26	800	1.7	2855	1.7	1954	3200	345	245	164	14	5	6	1874	29	15	9
27	710	1.8	2900	1.8	1874	3250	325	244	188	10	6	7	1888	30	30	21
28	715	1.9	3050	1.9	1888	3290	544	350	178	9	7	8	1466	33	31	22
29	720	2.0	3055	2.0	1466	3300	555	461	195	8	8	9	1234	21	35	23
30	722	2.1	2950	2.1	1234	3333	556	329	200	7	9	3	1555	23	30	21
31	744	1.6	2705	1.9	2855	4025	852	310	185	11	6	7	1850	19	27	12
32	731	1.8	2754	1.7	2860	2860	544	320	174	13	7	8	1950	20	26	15
33	726	1.8	2807	1.8	1870	2910	546	244	45	19	8	9	1000	21	25	19
34	739	2.0	2904	2.2	1760	3065	455	155	144	20	9	3	1200	23	27	17
35	740	2.1	3005	2.3	1865	3070	455	144	122	21	3	4	1212	25	28	16
36	753	2.3	3509	2.5	1958	2955	744	454	123	23	4	2	1235	29	29	20
37	752	2.2	3101	2.6	2021	3335	488	234	110	25	2	3	1239	30	30	21
38	762	2.4	3306	2.4	2013	3355	443	299	122	29	3	4	1359	33	31	22
39	767	2.1	3501	2.5	1015	3877	566	328	135	30	4	5	1596	15	35	23
40	738	2.1	2900	2.1	1750	3050	450	150	144	20	9	3	1234	13	42	26
41	741	2.2	3000	2.2	1890	3055	444	145	122	21	3	4	1235	19	40	27
42	750	2.3	3500	2.3	1900	2950	750	450	123	23	4	2	1239	20	19	10
43	751	2.4	3100	2.4	2001	3330	486	230	110	25	2	3	1359	21	18	11
44	760	2.5	3300	2.5	2011	3350	444	290	122	29	3	4	1596	23	17	15
45	765	2.6	3500	2.6	1000	3800	564	320	135	30	4	5	1954	25	16	10
46	744	2.7	3600	2.7	1250	3850	412	230	145	33	5	6	1874	29	15	9
47	750	2.8	3700	2.8	1850	2800	423	210	155	35	6	7	1888	30	30	21
48	755	2.9	4000	2.9	1950	2200	485	205	175	39	7	8	1466	33	31	22
49	725	1.3	2200	1.3	2600	3300	555	135	200	15	2	3	2001	18	30	17
50	743	1.4	2300	1.4	2650	3500	666	145	201	19	3	4	2011	17	33	20

REFERENCES

1. Dustkobilovich R. O., Laylo A. Types of modern lectures in higher education, technology of their design and organization //Проблемы современной науки и образования. – 2020. – №. 12-1 (157). – С. 41-46.
2. Рахимов О. Д., Манзаров Ю. Х., Ашурова Л. Ўзбекистон олий таълим тизимида дастлабки форсайт тадқиқотлар //Современное образование (Узбекистан). – 2021. – №. 4 (101). – С. 16-22.

3. Rakhimov O. D., Kh M. Y., Ashurova L. Initial foresight studies in the higher education system of Uzbekistan //Modern education (Uzbekistan).–2021. – 2021. – Т. 4. – №. 101. – С. 16-22.
4. Рахимов О. Д., Эшмухамедов Л. М., Ашурова Л. МУСТАҚИЛ ТАЪЛИМНИ РАҚАМЛИ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАР АСОСИДА ТАШКИЛ ЭТИШ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯСИ: Рахимов Октябрь Дусткабилович, Қарши муҳандислик-иқтисодиёт институти “Экология ва меҳнат муҳофазаси” кафедраси профессори Эшмухамедов Латиф Маҳмаюсуфович, Қарши муҳандислик-иқтисодиёт институти “Экология ва меҳнат муҳофазаси” кафедраси ассистенти Ашурова Лайло, Қарши муҳандислик-иқтисодиёт институти “Экология ва меҳнат муҳофазаси” кафедраси ассистенти //Образование и инновационные исследования международный научно-методический журнал. – 2022. – №. 6.
5. Rakhimov O. et al. Methodology for using foresight technology in training future ecologists in Uzbekistan //E3S Web of Conferences. – EDP Sciences, 2023. – Т. 462. – С. 03048.
6. Rakhimov O., Ashurova L., Artikbekova F. Hydraulic transport in small livestock farms //E3S Web of Conferences. – EDP Sciences, 2021. – Т. 274. – С. 03003.
7. Rakhimov O. D., Ashurova L. THE MAIN FACTORS AND CRITERIA OF QUALITY EDUCATION //GOLDEN BRAIN. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 31. – С. 163-169.
8. Ashurova L. METHODOLOGY OF USING TELECOMMUNICATION STUDY PROJECTS IN INDEPENDENT EDUCATION //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 17. – С. 135-140.
9. Ashurova L. ON THE TECHNOLOGY FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENTIFIC AND CREATIVE ACTIVITY IN STUDENTS //Innovative Development in Educational Activities. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 23. – С. 294-298.
10. Rakhimov O. D., Sh F. S., Ashurova L. Foresight as a technology for forecasting the development of the use of digital technologies in the higher education sector of Uzbekistan //The phenomenon of market economy: from the origins to the present day. Development institutions and information technologies in innovative solutions. – 2022. – С. 167-175.
11. Husanovich S. B., Ravshanovich B. Z., Laylo A. ANALYSIS OF DEVELOPMENTAL EDUCATION MODELS //Проблемы науки. – 2020. – №. 11 (59). – С. 86-90.
12. Рахимов О. Д., Файзиева Ш. Ш., Ашурова Л. Форсайт как технология прогнозирования развития применения цифровых технологий в секторе высшего образования Узбекистана //Феномен рыночного хозяйства: от истоков до наших

- дней. Институты развития и информационные технологии в инновационных решениях. – 2022. – С. 167-175.
13. Shomurotov B. H., Boyirov Z. R., Ashurova L. ANALYSIS OF DEVELOPMENTAL EDUCATION MODELS //Проблемы науки. – 2020. – №. 11. – С. 86-90.
 14. Ashurova L., Uralov M. BINO VA INSHOOTLAR XAVFSIZLIGI //FANINI O 'QITISHNING BA'ZI JIHATLARI//Interpretation and researches.–2024.
 15. Ashurova L., Uralov M. «BINO VA INSHOOTLAR XAVFSIZLIGI» FANINI O 'QITISHNING BA'ZI JIHATLARI //Interpretation and researches. – 2024.
 16. Ashurova L. ZILZILA, KELIB CHIQISH SABABLARI VA OQIBATLARI //GOLDEN BRAIN. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 423-431.
 17. Ashurova L. FIRES IN TECHNOSPHERE AND PRINCIPLES OF PROTECTION AGAINST THEM //Innovative Development in Educational Activities. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 20. – С. 81-86.
 18. Laylo A. ISHLAB CHQARISH XONALARI HAVOSINI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH UCHUN KONDITSIONER USKUNASINING ISHINI QIYOSIY TAHLIL QILISH VA UNI MODELLASHTIRISH //Sanoatda raqamli texnologiyalar/Цифровые технологии в промышленности. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 184-192.
 19. ASHUROVA L. ПРОБЛЕМЫ СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКИ И ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ //ПРОБЛЕМЫ СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКИ И ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ Учредители: Олимп. – С. 41-46.
 20. Маматов Ф. М., Шодмонов Г. Д. Обоснование конструктивной схемы комбинированного агрегата для подготовки почвы к посеву бахчевых //European research. – 2018. – №. 1 (35). – С. 10-14.
 21. Murtozevich M. F., Halilovich M. S., Dustmurodovich S. G. Dump ripper for soil protection from water erosion //European science review. – 2018. – №. 7-8. – С. 245-246.
 22. Мирзаев Б. С., Мардонов Ш. Х., Шодмонов Г. Д. О качестве рыхления почвы рыхлителем с рабочими органами наклонного типа //European research. – 2018. – №. 1 (35). – С. 15-18.
 23. Mamatov F. M., Mardonov S. H., Shodmonov G. D. DUMP RIPPER FOR SOIL PROTECTION FROM WATER EROSION //European Science Review. – 2018. – №. 7-8. – С. 245-246.
 24. Чуянов Д. Ш. и др. ПОЛИЗ ЭКИНЛАРИ ЭКИШ УЧУН ТУПРОҚНИ ТАЙЁРЛАЙДИГАН КОМБИНАЦИЯЛАШГАН АГРЕГАТ КОРПУСЛАРИНИНГ

- ПАРАМЕТРЛАРИ //Иновацион технологиялар. – 2021. – №. Спецвыпуск 1. – С. 146-150.
25. Шодмонов Ф. Д., ўғли Хидиров М. Қ. АВТОТРАНСПОРТ ЧИҚИНДИ ГАЗЛАРИ ЗАРАРЛИЛИГИНИ КАМАЙТИРИШНИНГ ЗАМОНАВИЙ УСУЛЛАРИ //INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 18. – С. 140-147.
26. Чуюнов Д. и др. КОМБИНАЦИЯЛАШГАН АГРЕГАТ ЮМШАТКИЧЛАРИНИНГ ЎЗARO ЖОЙЛАШИШИНИ АСОСЛАШ //Innovatsion texnologiyalar. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 4. – С. 61-63.
27. Shodmonov G., Xidirov M., Boymurodov S. AVTOMOBILLARNING ELEKTR VA ELEKTRON IHOZLARINI DIAGNOSTIKALASH //Академические исследования в современной науке. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 20. – С. 57-61.
28. Chuyanov D. et al. Parameters of slitter for embedding manure in soil for melon crops //E3S Web of Conferences. – EDP Sciences, 2023. – Т. 401. – С. 04048.
29. Чуюнов Д. Ш., Шодмонов Г. Д. ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЕ ОПТИМАЛЬНЫХ ПАРАМЕТРОВ СТАЛКИВАТЕЛЯ НАВОЗА //Вестник науки и образования. – 2023. – №. 12 (143)-2. – С. 5-9.
30. Чуюнов Д. Ш., Шодмонов Г. Д. ОБОСНОВАНИЕ ОСНОВНЫХ ПАРАМЕТРОВ ЦЕЛЕВАТЕЛЯ ДЛЯ ЗАДЕЛКИ НАВОЗА //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 14. – С. 1017-1023.
31. Dostmurodovich G. S. ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF FUNDS IN THE FIELD OF LABOR PROTECTION //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF EUROPEAN RESEARCH OUTPUT. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 57-61.
32. Dostmurodovich G. S. LABOR PROTECTION WHEN WORKING AT HEIGHTS //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 31-38.
33. Shodmonov G. “FAVQULODDA VAZIYATLAR VA FUQARO MUHOFAZASI” FANING MAQSAD VA VAZIFALARI //Interpretation and researches. – 2024.
34. Чуюнов Д. Ш. и др. ПОЛИЗ ЭКИНЛАРИ ЕТИШТИРИШДА ТУПРОҚКА ИШЛОВ БЕРИШ ВА ЭКИШНИНГ ЯНГИ УСУЛИ //Иновацион технологиялар. – 2021. – №. Спецвыпуск 2. – С. 53-56.
35. Чуюнов Д. Ш. и др. ПОЛИЗ ЭКИНЛАРИ ЕТИШТИРИШ УЧУН ЭНЕРГИЯ-РЕСУРСТЕЖАМКОР ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ ВА МАШИНА //Иновацион технологиялар. – 2020. – №. Спецвыпуск. – С. 78-82.

36. Маматов Ф. М., Чуянов Д. Ш., Шодмонов ҒД Э. М. И. Далаларни полиз экинлари экиш учун тайёрлайдиган комбинациялашган агрегатнинг параметрларини асослаш //Innovatsion texnologiyalar.–Қарши. – 2018. – №. 4. – С. 44-48.
37. Mirzaev B. et al. Parameters of the soil-holding part of the slurry spreader //E3S Web of Conferences. – EDP Sciences, 2023. – Т. 383. – С. 04016.
38. Chuyanov D. S., Mamatov F. M., Shodmonov G. D. Main parameters of manure sealer //E3S Web of Conferences. – EDP Sciences, 2023. – Т. 401. – С. 04031.
39. Shodmonov G. D., Xidirov MQ Avtotransport chiqindi gazlari zararliligini kamaytirishning zamonaviy usullari //International conference on innovative development of education. – 2022. – Т. 18. – С. 140-147.
40. Mamatov F., Karimov A., Shodmonov G. Study on the parameters of bars of the potato digger ploughshare //E3S Web of Conferences. – EDP Sciences, 2023. – Т. 434. – С. 03012.
41. Chuyanov D., Shodmonov G. Energy-saving technology and machinery for growing melons //International Journal of Innovations in Engineering Research and Technology. – 2020. – №. 1. – С. 1-7.
42. Shodmonov G. D. et al. MEHNAT MUHOFAZASI FANINING RIVOJLANISH TARIXI VA BOSHQA FANLAR BILAN O ‘ZARO BOG ‘LIQLIGI //GOLDEN BRAIN. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 3. – С. 149-153.
43. Chuyanov D. et al. Traction resistance of the combined machine plough //E3S Web of Conferences. – EDP Sciences, 2021. – Т. 264. – С. 04036.
44. Mamatov F. et al. Potato digger with a digging workpart of the " Paraplaw" type //E3S Web of Conferences. – EDP Sciences, 2023. – Т. 365. – С. 04021.
45. Murtozevich M. F. et al. New technology and combined machine for preparing soil for sowing gourds //European science review. – 2018. – №. 1-2. – С. 234-236.
46. Chuyanov D. et al. Soil preparation machine parameters for the cultivation of cucurbitaceous crops //IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering. – IOP Publishing, 2020. – Т. 883. – №. 1. – С. 012122.
47. Mirzaev B. et al. Combined machine for preparing soil for cropping of melons and gourds //IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science. – IOP Publishing, 2019. – Т. 403. – №. 1. – С. 012158.

48. Мурадов С. ПРОБЛЕМЫ ТУШЕНИЯ ПОЖАРОВ КЛАССА Е ЛИЧНЫМ СОСТАВОМ ПОЖАРНОЙ ОХРАНЫ В МИРЕ //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 758-773.
49. Rayimkulov A., Murodov S. Some Issues of Safety in the Use of Tower Cranes Used in Construction Projects //JournalNX. – С. 301-308.
50. Dildora X., Sirojiddin M. O ‘zbekiston respublikasi hududida seysmoaktiv hududlar va zilzilaning xavfliligi //Innovative Development in Educational Activities. – 2024. – С. 167-172.
51. ЎҒЛИ Р. Х. Ф., СИРОЖИДДИН М. ИЗУЧЕНИЯ УСЛОВИЯ ТРУДА В КОМПАНИИ ЕВРОПЫ. МУРАДОВ СИРОЖИДДИН //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 10.
52. O‘G‘LI M. S. H. ANALYSIS OF “MEASURES TO ENSURE OCCUPATIONAL SAFETY IN THE FIELD OF CARGO TRANSPORTATION AND LOADING.” //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 9.
53. Sirojiddin M., Umurzoq E. INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT OF WORKING CONDITIONS AND ENVIRONMENT THROUGH THE KAIZEN METHOD //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 12. – С. 42-47.
54. Rakhimov O. D., Muradov S. H. Digitalization of Instructions on Labor Protection and Safety Techniques //European journal of life safety and stability (EJLSS). – 2022. – Т. 24. – С. 80-86.
55. Muradov S. H. o ‘g ‘li, & Zayniyev, UU o ‘g ‘li.(2023). PRINCIPLES OF PASSING AND DOCUMENTING INSTRUCTIONS ON SAFETY TECHNIQUES //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – Т. 2. – №. 14. – С. 116-119.
56. Muradov S. ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF PROFITS IN THE FIELD OF LABOR PROTECTION //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 1239-1245.
57. МУРАДОВ С. ИЗУЧЕНИЯ ОХРАНА ТРУДЫ НА ПРОИЗВОДСТВЕ КОРЕИ //ХӨДӨЛМӨР, НИЙГМИЙН ХАРИЛЦАА СУДЛАЛ. – 2023. – С. 242-247.
58. СИРОЖИДДИН М. РАЖАБОВ ХУРШИД ФАХРИДДИН ЎҒЛИ. ИЗУЧЕНИЯ УСЛОВИЯ ТРУДА В КОМПАНИИ ЕВРОПЫ. МУРАДОВ СИРОЖИДДИН //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2023. – Т. 10. – С. 27.

59. Husan o'g'li M. S., Utkir o'g'li Z. U. PRINCIPLES OF PASSING AND DOCUMENTING INSTRUCTIONS ON SAFETY TECHNIQUES //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2023. – T. 11.
60. Мурадов С. Определение отдыха и отпусков на основании нового трудового кодекса //Aholi bandligi sohasidagi davlat siyosatining amalga oshirishning dolzarb masalalari. – 2023. – T. 10. – №. 26. – C. 17-21.
61. Muradov S. H. Safarov Sh. O ' . MEHNAT SHAROITLARI VA MUHITINI "KAIZEN" USULI YORDAMIDA TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING INNOVATSION YECHIMLARI //PAXTA TOZALASH, TO 'QIMACHILIK VA YENGIL SANOAT SOHALARINING TEXNOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH. – 2023. – C. 90-92.
62. Sirojiddin M. Mehnatni muhofaza qilishning tashkiliy-psixologik asoslaridagi mavjud muammolar //Ekologiya, aholi xavfsizligi va mehnat muhofazasining hozirgi kundagi dolzarb masalalari va istiqbollari. – 2023. – C. 133-137.
63. Sirojiddin M. Mehnat sharoitlari va muhitini "kaizen" usuli yordamida takomillashtirishning innovatsion yechimlari //Ekologiya, aholi xavfsizligi va mehnat muhofazasining hozirgi kundagi dolzarb masalalari va istiqbollari. – 2023. – C. 249-253.
64. Muradov S. H. o 'g 'li, & Egamov, DS o 'g 'li.(2023). INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS TO PROTECT WORKERS FROM DANGEROUS GAS AND TOXIC SUBSTANCES IN HAZARDOUS INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – T. 2. – №. 14. – C. 340-342.
65. Muradov S. ASSESSMENT OF THE CHEMICAL SITUATION IN AN ACCIDENT IN FACILITIES USING KTZM //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 1142-1152.
66. Sirojiddin M. Mehnatni muhofaza qilish sohasida yuk ortish va tushirish ishlaridagi yukchilar uchun ishlarning xavfsizligi kategori va qoidalari tahlili //Ekologiya, aholi xavfsizligi va mehnat muhofazasining hozirgi kundagi dolzarb masalalari va istiqbollari. – 2023. – C. 232-242.
67. Sirojiddin M. Mehnatni muhofaza qilishning rivojlanish tarixiy bosqichlarini o 'rganish //Ekologiya, aholi xavfsizligi va mehnat muhofazasining hozirgi kundagi dolzarb masalalari va istiqbollari. – 2023. – C. 243-248.
68. Sirojiddin M. Sanoat korxonalarini rahbar va mutaxassislarining mehnat muhofazasi bo 'yicha bilimlarini tekshirishni raqamli texnologiyalar asosida tashkil etishning ahamiyati

- //Ekologiya, aholi xavfsizligi va mehnat muhofazasining hozirgi kundagi dolzarb masalalari va istiqbollari. – 2023. – С. 146-150.
69. Sirojiddin M. Xavfli sanoat korxonalarida ishchilarni xavfli gaz va zaxarli moddalar ta'siridan himoya qilishga qaratilgan inovatsion yechimlar //Ekologiya, aholi xavfsizligi va mehnat muhofazasining hozirgi kundagi dolzarb masalalari va istiqbollari. – 2023. – С. 402-405.
70. Muradov S. CONSTRUCTION-INSTALLATION ISHLARIDA KUTARAMA KRANLARDAN USE FUNDAMENTAL SECURITY OF SUPPLY //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 786-792.
71. СИРОЖИДДИН М. НЕКОТОРЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ ГРУЗОПОДЪЕМНЫХ КРАНОВ В СТРОИТЕЛЬНО-МОНТАЖНЫХ РАБОТАХ //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 167-177.
72. Raximov O. D. Muradov SH Sanoat korxonalari rahbari va mutaxassislarini mehnat muhofazasi bo'yicha o'qitish va bilimlarini sinovdan o'tkazishni raqamlashtirish //INTELLEKT. MONOGRAFIYA. – 2023.
73. O'G'LI M. S. H. Mehnatni muhofaza qilishning rivojlanish tarixiy bosqichlarini o'rganish //Aholi bandligi sohasidagi davlat siyosatining amalga oshirishning dolzarb masalalari. – 2023. – Т. 10. – №. 26. – С. 8-16.
74. Muradov S. ENSURING SAFETY OF WORKERS IN CONSTRUCTION //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 493-501.
75. Muradov S. Ishlab chiqarishdagi avariyalarni o'rganish va tahlil qilish //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 16. – С. 474-477.
76. СИРОЖИДДИН учитель-стажер М. Каршинский инженерноэкономический институт кафедра «Охрана труда и техника безопасности» Республики Узбекистан.(2024). НЕКОТОРЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ ГРУЗОПОДЪЕМНЫХ КРАНОВ В СТРОИТЕЛЬНО-МОНТАЖНЫХ РАБОТАХ. Zenodo //НЕКОТОРЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ.
77. Мурадов С. PRINCIPLES OF ENSURING THE SAFETY OF USING LIFTING CRANES IN CONSTRUCTION-ASSEMBLY WORKS //MODERN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 933-939.
78. Husan o'g'li M. S. Sanoat korxonalari rahbar va mutaxassislarining mehnat muhofazasi bo'yicha bilimlarini tekshirishni raqamli texnologiyalar asosida tashkil etishning ahamiyati

- //Aholi bandligi sohasidagi davlat siyosatining amalga oshirishning dolzarb masalalari. – 2023. – T. 10. – №. 26. – C. 180-183.
79. Muradov S., Xujaqulov A., Eshmuxamedov L. ORGANIZING TRAINING ON THE CAUSES OF EMERGENCY SITUATIONS, CHARACTERISTICS AND ACTION AT THE FOCUS OF INJURY //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 247-264.
80. Muradov S., Usmonov H. MEHNATNI MUHOFAZA QILISHNING RIVOJLANISH TARIXIY BOSQICHLARINI ORGANIZIRISH //Interpretation and researches. – 2024.
81. Muradov S. CHEMICAL STATUS ASSESSMENT AND ANALYSIS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 455-463.
82. Muradov S. MAIN INDICATORS OF LABOR PROTECTION MEASURES EFFICIENCY //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 473-484.
83. Muradov S. STUDY AND ANALYSIS OF WORKING ACCIDENTS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 444-454.
84. Muradov S. INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT OF WORKING CONDITIONS AND ENVIRONMENT THROUGH THE KAIZEN METHOD //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 485-492.
85. Sirojiddin M. KTZM QO ‘LLANILADIGAN OBYEKTlardagi AVARIYADA KIMYOVIY HOLATNI BAHOLASH. – 2024.
86. O‘G E. L. A. A. et al. PHYSIOLOGICAL AND HYGIENE BASIS OF HUMAN LABOR ACTIVITY //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 11.
87. Husan o‘g‘li M. S., Shavkat o‘g‘li E. D. INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS TO PROTECT WORKERS FROM DANGEROUS GAS AND TOXIC SUBSTANCES IN HAZARDOUS INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2023. – C. 11-17.
88. Muradov S. THE SIGNIFICANCE OF ORGANIZING THE EXAMINATION OF KNOWLEDGE OF LABOR PROTECTION OF MANAGERS AND SPECIALISTS OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES ON THE BASIS OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 805-817.
89. Muradov S. ANALYSIS OF JOB SAFETY CATEGORY AND RULES FOR LOADING AND UNLOADING WORKERS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 788-804.

90. Muradov S. DEFINITION OF REST AND LEAVES BASED ON THE NEW LABOR CODE //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 774-787.
91. Muradov S. EMERGENCY EPIDEMIOLOGICAL, EPIZOOTIC AND EPIPHYTOTIC SITUATIONS. PARTICULARLY DANGEROUS INFECTIONS THAT CAUSE RARE DISEASES SUCH AS PLAGUE AND YELLOW FEVER //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 703-728.
92. Sirojiddin M. MEHNAT MUHOFAZASI SOHASIDAGI MAQSABLARNING IQTISODIY TAHLILI. – 2024.
93. Muradov S. EPISOTOTIC SITUATIONS, THEIR PREVENTION //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 831-851.
94. Muradov S. CAUSES, CHARACTERISTICS AND ACTIONS OF THE POPULATION IN THE FOCUSES OF DAMAGE OF EMERGENCIES OF A MAN-GENIC CHARACTER //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 729-744.
95. Sultonova D. N., qizi Siddiqova M. A. COLOR SCHEME IN THE FORMATION OF THE ARTISTIC ENVIRONMENT OF THE INTERIOR OF MODERN EDUCATIONAL CENTERS //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 14. – C. 109-115.
96. Muradov S. et al. EMERGENCY EPIDEMIOLOGICAL, EPIZOOTIC AND EPIPHYTOTIC SITUATIONS. PARTICULARLY DANGEROUS INFECTIONS THAT CAUSE INFECTIOUS AND COMMON DISEASES //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 281-318.
97. Muradov S. et al. STANDARDS OF SAFETY REQUIREMENTS FOR PRESSURE CABINETS, APPARATUS AND GAS EQUIPMENT //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 159-180.
98. Husan ogli M. S., Hamidulla o'g'li X. X. Siddiqova Madinabonu Asatilla qizi.(2021). NEW INNOVATIVE ENGINEERING SOLUTIONS TO THE PROBLEMS OF SIGNALIZATION AND SECURITY SYSTEMS //European Journal of Life Safety and Stability (2660-9630). – T. 2. – C. 28-30.
99. Muradov S. et al. STUDY OF THE HISTORICAL STAGES OF THE SCIENCE OF LABOR PROTECTION //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 350-365.
100. Muradov S. et al. CHECKING KNOWLEDGE OF LABOR PROTECTION //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 386-400.

101. Muradov S. et al. MOVEMENT OF CHICTONIC PLATES, ORIGIN OF EARTHQUAKES //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 401-415.
102. Muradov S. et al. MAIN CONTENT AND COMPONENT PARTS OF THE SCIENCE" SAFETY OF CONSTRUCTION OF BUILDINGS AND CONSTRUCTIONS" //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 335-349.
103. Muradov S. et al. ANALYSIS OF SECURITY CATEGORY AND RULES FOR CARRIERS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 366-385.
104. Muradov S. et al. ADMINISTRATIVE BUILDINGS AND THEIR REQUIREMENTS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 257-280.
105. Muradov S. et al. STABILITY CALCULATION OF LOAD LIFT VEHICLES //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 205-234.
106. Muradov S. et al. CONTENT AND ESSENCE OF THE LAW AND LEGAL DOCUMENTS ON THE PROTECTION OF THE POPULATION AND TERRITORIES FROM EMERGENCIES //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 168-204.
107. Muradov S. et al. CAUSES OF NATURAL EMERGENCIES //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 92-130.
108. Muradov S. et al. ANALYSIS OF SAFETY REQUIREMENTS OF EQUIPMENT WORKING UNDER HIGH PRESSURE //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 131-167.
109. Qizi S. M. A. et al. O ‘QUV BINOLARI VA O ‘QUV MARKAZLARINI RANG YECHIMINI RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR HAMDA SUN’IY INTELLEKT ORQALI LOYIHALASH //Raqamli iqtisodiyot (Цифровая экономика). – 2024. – №. 6. – С. 325-332.
110. Qizi S. M. A., Namazovna S. D. JAMOAT BINOLARI VA O ‘QUV MARKAZLARI UCHUN TASVIRIY SAN’AT VA RANG YECHIMINI LOYIHALASHDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNING O ‘RNI //Raqamli iqtisodiyot (Цифровая экономика). – 2024. – №. 6. – С. 333-340.
111. Muradov S. et al. NATURAL EMERGENCIES, INFECTIOUS DISEASES //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 416-441.
112. Мурадов С., Каримов Б., Сиддиқова М. ПРОБЛЕМЫ ТУШЕНИЯ ПОЖАРОВ КЛАССА //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 600-618.

113. Muradov S., Karimov B., Siddiqova M. FAVQULODDA VAZIYATLARNING VUJUDGA KELISHI SABABLARI, VA FAVQULODDA VAZIYATLARDA HARAKAT QILISHGA O‘RGATISHNI TASHKIL ETISH //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 5. – C. 554-573.
114. Muradov S., Karimov B., Siddiqova M. MEHNATNI MUHOFAZA QILISHDA YUK KO‘TARISH VOSITALARINI MUSTAHKAMLIKKA HISOBLASH //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 5. – C. 636-655.
115. Muradov S., Karimov B., Siddiqova M. FAVQULODDA VAZIYATLAR VA ULARNING TURLARI, TABIIY TUSDAGI FAVQULODDA VAZIYATLAR //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 5. – C. 656-680.
116. Muradov S., Karimov B., Siddiqova M. ISHLAB CHIQRISHDA O‘TA YUQORI BOSIM OSTIDA ISHLOVCHI USKUNLARNING XAVFSIZLIK TALABLARI TAXLILI TEXNIK ASOSLARI //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 5. – C. 681-703.
117. Muradov S., Siddiqova M., Karimov B. KIMYOVIY AVARIYA HOLATINI BAHOLASH VA TAXLIL QILISH //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 5.
118. Muradov S., Siddiqova M., Karimov B. LABOR PROTECTION MEASURES EFFICIENCY //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 5. – C. 774-793.
119. Muradov S., Siddiqova M., Karimov B. KUCHLI TA‘SIR ETUVCHI ZAHARLI MODDALAR AVARIYALARIDA KIMYOVIY HOLATNI BAHOLASH //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 5.
120. Muradov S., Karimov B., Asatilla M. MAMURIY BINOLAR VA ULARNING TAVSIFLANISHI //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 5.
121. Мурадов С., Каримов Б., Сиддиқова М. ОТПУСКОВ НА ОСНОВАНИИ НОВОГО ТРУДОВОГО КОДЕКСА //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 5. – C. 619-635.
122. Muradov S., Siddiqova M., Karimov B. CONDITIONS AND ENVIRONMENT THROUGH THE KAIZEN METHOD //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 5. – C. 794-808.
123. Muradov S., Karimov B., Siddiqova M. QURILISH ASHYOLARINING MEXANIK XOSSALARI //NEW RENASSAINCE CONFERENCE. – 2024. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 144-164.

124. Muradov S., Karimov B., Siddiqova M. QURILISH ASHYOLARINING TUZILISHI VA TASNIFI //NEW RENASSAINCE CONFERENCE. – 2024. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 98-121.
125. Muradov S., Karimov B., Siddiqova M. QURILISH ASHYOLARI TARKIBINI ILMIY ASOSLASH USULLARI //NEW RENASSAINCE CONFERENCE. – 2024. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 122-143.
126. Muradov S., Siddiqova M., Karimov B. STUDY AND ANALYSIS OF ACCIDENTS IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 6. – C. 16-31.
127. Muradov S., Siddiqova M., Karimov B. PARTICULARLY DANGEROUS INFECTIONS THAT CAUSE CONTAGIOUS AND COMMON DISEASES //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 6. – C. 32-64.
128. Muradov S., Karimov B., Siddiqova M. FAVQULODDA VAZIYATLARDA TIZIMIGA DOIR QONUNCHILIK //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 5. – C. 574-599.
129. Muradov S., Karimov B., Asatilla M. “BINO VA INSHOOTLARNI XAVFSIZLIGI” FANINING ASOSIY MAZMUNI //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 5. – C. 809-824.
130. Рахимов О. АЙРИМ ХОРИЖИЙ ДАВЛАТЛАР ТАЖРИБАСИДА НОТАРИАЛ ФАОЛИЯТНИ ТАШКИЛ ЭТИШ ВА НАЗОРАТНИ АМАЛГА ОШИРИШНИНГ ЎЗИГА ХОС ЖИҲАТЛАРИ.
131. Dustkabilovich R. O. THE EFFECT OF THE APPLICATION OF INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS.
132. Рахимов О. Д. Исследование процесса подачи кормосмесей пониженной влажности коловратным насосом на малых свинофермах. – 1992.
133. ТРЕГУБ Л. И., РАХИМОВ О. Д., ПРАВАТОВ Н. М. Установка для подачи влажных кормов. – 1993.
134. Dustkabilovich R. O. NECESSITY OF LIVE MODERN LECTURES IN HIGHER EDUCATION AND ITS TYPES //Проблемы науки. – 2020. – №. 10 (58). – C. 65-69.
135. Dustkabilovich R. O. et al. Description of pedagogical technology and problematic teaching technology //Проблемы современной науки и образования. – 2020. – №. 2 (147). – C. 59-62.

- 136.Рахимов О. Д. ИНТЕРНЕТ-ОБУЧЕНИЕ МУЗЫКЕ //Рекомендовано к печати Ученым советом Института психологии имени ГС Костюка НАПН Украины (Протокол № 14 от 28 декабря 2020). – 2020. – С. 412.
- 137.РАХИМОВ О. Д., МАНЗАРОВ Ю. Х., АШУРОВА Л. PRIMARY FORESIGHT RESEARCH IN THE SYSTEM OF HIGHER EDUCATION IN UZBEKISTAN //Современное образование (Узбекистан). – 2021. – №. 4. – С. 16-22.
- 138.Рахимов О. Д., Рахимова Д. О. Форсайт исследование по прогнозированию развития цифровизации высшего образования Республики Узбекистан. – 2021.
- 139.Рахимов О. Д., Ашурова Л. ЎҚИТИШНИНГ ИНТЕРАКТИВ УСЛУБЛАРИДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШ САМАРАДОРЛИГИ //RESEARCH AND EDUCATION. – 2022. – С. 332.
- 140.Rakhimov O., Nuriddinova S. THE SIGNIFICANCE OF APPLYING PROJECT METHOD TECHNOLOGY IN INDEPENDENT STUDY OF THE SUBJECT OF BIOLOGY //Евразийский журнал медицинских и естественных наук. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 11. – С. 375-380.
- 141.Dustkabilovich R. O. MASOFAVIY TA'LIM TEXNOLOGIYALARI TASNIFI //International journal of scientific researchers (IJSR) INDEXING. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 2.
- 142.Рахимов О. Д., Рахматов М. И. ЦИФРОВАЯ ЭКОНОМИКА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ: ЦИФРОВИЗАЦИЯ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ И УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ОХРАНОЙ ТРУДА НА ПРОМЫШЛЕННЫХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯХ //Феномен рыночного хозяйства: от истоков до наших дней. Трансформация экономических систем в контексте турбулентного развития. – 2023. – С. 246-253.
- 143.OD R. et al. Methodology of Education of Specialists in Industrial Enterprises using for Site Technology on the Effect of Electricity on the Human Body. – 2023.
- 144.Raximov O. D. GLOBALLASHUV DAVRIDA TA'LIM TIZIMI MUAMMOLARI //GOLDEN BRAIN. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 10-16.
- 145.Raximov O. D. i dr. Zamonaviy ta'lim texnologiyalari //Т.:“Fan va texnologiya nashriyoti.–2013.
- 146.Шодиева М., Рахимов О. Д. Ўқитувчилар малака ошириш тизимида таълим сифатини таъминлашда ўқув-услугий мажмуаларнинг ўрни //Современное образование (Узбекистан). – 2017. – №. 1. – С. 24-28.

147. Азаренкова Г. М. и др. ИНСТИТУЦИОНАЛЬНО-ВОСПРОИЗВОДСТВЕННЫЙ МЕХАНИЗМ ФОРМАЦИОННОЙ РАЗВИЛКИ: ПРИНЦИПЫ, ФОРМЫ, ИНСТРУМЕНТЫ. – 2021.
148. Рахимов О. Д., Чоршанбиев З. Э. Форсайт как инструмент прогнозирования применения информационно-цифровой технологии в высшем образовании республики Узбекистана //Феномен рыночного хозяйства: от истоков до наших дней. Синтез цифровых технологий и инновационных решений. – 2021. – С. 326-335.
149. Raximov O. D. Manzarov Yu. X., Ashurova L. O ‘zbekiston oliy ta’lim tizimida dastlabki forsayt tadqiqotlar //Sovremennoye obrazovaniye (Uzbekistan).–2021. – 2021. – Т. 4. – №. 101. – С. 16-22.
150. Anisimov K. V. et al. Phenomenon of market economy: business concepts of innovations in theoretical and practical solutions. – 2022.